

Complexes of Copper with Isonitrosoacetylacetone

S. B. KHATAVKAR and B. C. HALDAR

Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry Laboratory, The Institute of Science, Bombay.

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$\text{Cu}(\text{INAA})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{INAA})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ have been prepared and their structures have been investigated by magnetic and spectral measurements.

It is reported that a green coloured compound¹, probably of the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{INAA})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, is formed by the reaction of copper acetate and isonitrosoacetylacetone (HINAA) in aqueous solution. However, its structure has not been investigated. In the present study $\text{Cu}(\text{INAA})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{INAA})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been prepared and their structures have been investigated by magnetic and spectral measurements

Experimental

Chemicals and solvents used are of A. R. quality. The preparation of HINAA² and the description of the instruments employed for magnetic and spectral studies³ are reported elsewhere.

Preparation of olive-green $\text{Cu}(\text{INAA})_2$ (I)

An alcoholic solution of isonitroso-acetylacetone (HINAA) and an ammoniacal solution of copper (II) chloride were mixed in the molar ratio of 2:1 and the pH of the mixture was raised to 4.3 by adding dilute ammonium hydroxide solution. An olive-green compound separated rapidly on stirring. It was filtered, washed repeatedly with water, dried at 110° and analysed. (Found Cu . 19 75% C=37.73%, H 3 6%, N=8 5%; expected for $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{NO}_3)_2$, Cu 19 84%, C 37 56%, H 3 7% and N=8.7%).

Preparation of Pale-green $\text{Cu}(\text{INAA})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$. (II)

An aqueous ammoniacal solution of copper acetate was mixed with an alcoholic solution of HINAA that Copper HINAA ratio was 1:1. The pH of the mixture was raised to 4.5 by adding dilute ammonia solution. A pale-green compound separated rapidly. It was filtered, washed with water and acetone, dried at 105° and analysed. (Found Cu-23.58%, C-31.70%, H-4.40%, N-5.00%, expected for $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_6)$, Cu-23.61%, C-31.29%, H-4.10% and N-5.20%)

Discussion

The compounds I and II are insoluble in water and very sparingly soluble in most organic solvents. Their magnetic moments are substantially below the spin only value for one unpaired electron. The

magnetic moment of I changes from 1.08 B. M. to 1.26 B. M. over the temperature range 87°-295°K, while that of II varies from 0.91 B. M. to 1.03 B.M. in the range 83.50-240°K. Such sub-normal values of magnetic moments have been reported for many copper(II) complexes^{4,5}. The anomalous magnetic behaviour of I and II can be explained on the basis of antiferromagnetic interaction. The best fit for I is observed by assuming it to be a mixture of 29% of the monomeric form obeying the Curie-Weiss law with a magnetic moment of 1.9 B.M., corresponding to one unpaired electron, and 71% of the binuclear variety showing antiferromagnetic exchange interaction with exchange coupling constant, $J=300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $g=2$. The λ_M values for the dimeric form at various temperatures are calculated by using the equation derived by Bleaney and Bowers⁶.

$$\lambda_M = \frac{N\beta^2 g^2}{3kT} \cdot \frac{3}{3 + \exp(-J/kT)} + N\alpha$$

where terms have their usual significance. The value of $N\alpha$ is assumed to be 60×10^{-6} c.g s/mole. Curve A in Fig. 1 shows the agreement between the observed and calculated values. The magnetic moments of II at various temperatures in the range 83.5-240°K can be accounted for by assuming it to be a mixture of 25% of the monomeric form with a magnetic moment of 1.90 B.M. and 75% of the dimeric form exhibiting antiferromagnetic interaction with exchange coupling constant J being 300 cm^{-1} and $g=2$. The observed and calculated values for λ_M at various temperatures are represented in Curve B of Fig 1

The electronic spectra (Fig. 2) of I and II in methanol solution show peaks at 34.40 kK ($E=4768$) and 39.46 kK ($E=2738$) respectively, which are likely to be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions in the ligand. The shoulders at 28.5 kK, 25.00 kK and 17.5 kK in the spectrum of I may be assigned to charge transfer bands. However, it is possible that the shoulder near 17.5 kK arises due to a d-d transition. The diffuse reflectance spectrum (Fig. 3) (A) of I reveals a broad maximum at 14.5 kK, which is attributed to d-d transitions. The complex II in methanol solution does not show any absorption maximum in the visible region. However, its reflectance spectrum (Fig. 3B)

Fig. 2. Electronic Absorption Spectra of
 A-Cu (C₅H₈NO₂)₂,
 B-Cu (C₇H₁₁NO₂) Complexes in Methanol

The infra-red spectrum of II is very similar to that of I. The present investigation suggests that the complex II may be formulated as

Fig 3 Diffuse Reflectance Spectra of
 A $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{NO}_2)_2$
 B $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{11}\text{NO})$

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The likely structures for the dimeric forms of I and II, which exhibit anti-ferromagnetic interaction, are shown below

